

The interplay between EFL teachers' beliefs and application of post-reading strategies in secondary school reading comprehension

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Abstract

Teachers' beliefs determine their professional behaviours in applying the post-reading strategies which could in turn affect the students' reading comprehension achievements. This exploratory case study investigates the relationship between EFL teachers' beliefs and their application of post-reading strategies in secondary school reading comprehension classes. Using convenience sampling, six experienced EFL teachers were selected from a secondary school in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. Data were gathered through classroom observations and individual interviews, with qualitative analysis conducted via NVivo10. Findings reveal a noticeable gap between teachers' positive beliefs about the instructional value of post-reading strategies and their limited application in practice, largely due to time constraints and perceived instructional demands. The study concludes that despite recognizing the importance of post-reading strategies, teachers prioritize while-reading activities, impacting students' opportunities to fully engage with text interpretation and connecting it with their real-life experiences. These findings suggest a need for targeted teacher training and continuous professional development programs for EFL teachers on integrating post-reading strategies effectively within classroom constraints.

Keywords: Beliefs; EFL teachers; post-reading strategies; reading comprehension; secondary school

1. Introduction

Like many nations worldwide, English is taught as a foreign language in Ethiopia (MoE, 1994). To learn this vital international language, students need to master the basic language skills. Hence, for effective teaching and learning of the English language, EFL teachers should apply well-designed teaching procedures, and carefully chosen activities, methods, and strategies. Specifically, EFL teachers' instructional roles in teaching reading comprehension plays a critical role in students' language skills growth (Taye et al., 2018).

English as a foreign language teachers have an indispensable instructional role to assist their students in reading comprehension classes. Therefore, by applying the relevant reading strategies, EFL teachers need to

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assist their students in comprehending the text. Duffy, (2009) explained that reading strategies are classified under the three basic stages of reading comprehension lessons. These are pre-reading, while-reading, and post-reading. Hence, EFL teachers should implement such reading strategies while teaching reading comprehension. More specifically, during the pre-reading phase, teachers need to implement strategies to link the readers' schema (prior knowledge) with the new knowledge by predicting, improving interest in reading, and anticipating what will be read. Using the while-reading strategies, teachers can help students cope with new vocabulary and contexts, as well as bridges between existing knowledge and the new text. By applying the post-reading strategies, teachers can also help students to interpret, confirm predictions evaluate their understanding of the text, and make generalizations and connections to their own lives (Cekiso,2012).

1.1. Reading comprehension

Primarily, understanding the essence of reading comprehension would help to identify the instructional role of EFL teachers in using the post-reading strategies to teach reading comprehension lessons. Pardo (2004) states that reading comprehension considers how readers interact with the text and extract meaning by utilizing their prior knowledge and information. This definition, emphasizes that readers need to apply prior knowledge and information to comprehend the given text. Similarly, Grabe & Stoller (2019) describe reading comprehension as it is a meaning-making process of the relationship between the text, the reader's cognitive process, and their prior knowledge. Still, a comprehensive definition of reading comprehension is supplied by Pressley (2002) in terms of being a process involving integration of decoding ability, vocabulary knowledge, prior knowledge of the topic considered, and relevant strategies. From the above definitions given by various scholars, we can extract a combined meaning of reading comprehension. It is an active and interactive cognitive process in which the readers struggle to understand a particular text. This process requires the students to apply a wide range of reading strategies, prior knowledge, decoding ability, knowledge of vocabulary and grammar.

1.2. Teachers' Beliefs

Understanding reading comprehension provides a foundation for exploring teachers' beliefs, as their instructional decisions often align with their belief systems. A belief is a proposition which may be consciously or unconsciously held, is evaluative, in that it is acceptable as true by the individual and is therefore imbued with emotive commitment; further, it serves as a guide to thought and behavior (Borg, 2001). Likewise, Zheng (2009) stresses that understanding teachers' beliefs is crucial to comprehend their thought processes, pedagogical approaches, and teaching methodology. On the other hand, Ghaith (2004) explained that teachers' views are a comprehensive understanding of various factors related to attitudes about teaching and education, curricula, and the teaching profession in general, which has an impact on pedagogical goals. Based on the above definitions, we can deduce EFL teachers' practices of reading strategies might be guided by the belief systems they possess regarding the selection, planning and

implementation of reading strategies. Therefore, the researchers of this study want to examine the beliefs of EFL teachers particularly about the instructional importance of post-reading strategies, and the type and frequency of usage of such strategies in reading comprehension classes.

1.3. Previous Studies on the Relationship between Teachers' Beliefs and Application of Reading Strategies

Several studies have been conducted to find out the relationship between teachers' stated beliefs and their practices of the reading strategies. The following studies investigated this issue by considering the two main variables i.e., beliefs and use of reading strategies either in an integrated way or separately. For instance, Khonamri & Salimi (2010) studied quantitatively the interaction between EFL teachers' beliefs and their instructional practices concerning reading strategies. The study revealed that there is discrepancy between teachers' beliefs and their self-reported classroom practices. Similarly, Atinafu (2018) with mixed-methods approach, examined the interplay between teachers' beliefs and practices in reading strategy use. The results indicated teachers believe that reading strategy training is vital to enable learners to become effective readers. Besides, teachers use insufficient pre-reading strategies. However, the participants do not implement most of the while-reading and post-reading strategies. Also, Raouf Mustafa & Barany, (2023) scrutinized quantitatively the strategies used by English teachers. The study results indicated teachers believe that all reading strategies are essential when applied in EFL reading classes.

Likewise, Bamanger & Gashan, (2014) conducted a quantitative study emphasizing the EFL teachers' beliefs about the use of reading strategies. The results have shown that EFL teachers highlighted the significance of teaching reading strategies. Furthermore, the findings designated EFL teachers' beliefs about efficient strategies of reading meaningfully associate with what they actually do in the classroom. Moreover, Enyew & Melesse (2018) examined quantitatively the connection between beliefs college English instructors held about reading strategies. The study revealed that the participants held robust beliefs about reading strategies. However, they do not actually apply the strategies in their reading classes. In general, none of the above studies considered the interaction between EFL teachers' beliefs and use of reading strategies in teaching reading comprehension qualitatively. It is for this reason that the researchers of this study wanted to conduct this qualitative case study.

1.4. Theoretical Framework of the Study

The relationship between EFL teachers' beliefs and actual practices of reading strategies in general and the post-reading strategies in particular can be understood through the lens of relevant theories. This would help to ground the study conceptually. Accordingly, beliefs and practices, as to Guerra & Wubbena (2017) are complicatedly related. This shows that EFL teachers' beliefs and the instructional decisions they make to select and apply the reading comprehension strategies have considerable relationships. Strengthening this point, Pajares (1992) stresses that people act out behaviors in accordance with their beliefs.

A strategy is an action the teacher employs to meet one or more of teaching-learning objectives (Harmer, 2007). Teaching strategies can make a range of teaching approaches and techniques for reading instruction. The reading comprehension skill is the most significant skill in language teaching and learning. Hence, EFL teachers have key role to escalate the students' reading comprehension. To attain this, teachers practice diverse strategies when they teach reading comprehension. More specifically, teachers should implement the post-reading strategies intended to involve the students in text evaluation, reconstruction of the writer's opinion, summarizing the text, and relating the message with their own knowledge, experience, and feelings (Williams,1994). Therefore, before the actual reading comprehension class begins, EFL teachers need to select appropriate post-reading strategies and apply them in reading comprehension classes to assist students in comprehending the text better and extending initial understanding of the text.

1.5. Statement of the Problem

Several studies overseas have been conducted recently regarding the effect of pre-reading and post-reading strategies on students' reading comprehension skills. Imran Ahmed et.al., (2024); Tanjung (2019); Safrianti, (2020); Cekiso, (2012) are to mention a few. However, these studies followed experimental and quasi-experimental designs that are different from the study at hand.

In the Ethiopian context, few studies have been conducted regarding the interplay between secondary school EFL teachers' beliefs and practices of reading strategies in reading comprehension classes. Atinafu (2018) investigated the interplay between Bahir Dar Town Secondary School EFL teachers' beliefs and practice in reading strategy use. The study found teachers tend to believe that promoting reading strategy training is crucial in empowering learners to become efficient readers, although they do not train their students to use the strategies properly. Teachers try to use few pre-reading strategies; however, most of the while-reading and post-reading strategies do not appear to be employed. In the same vein, Regassa & Teshome (2015) conducted a study on Jimma and East Wollega Zone High School EFL teachers' belief systems of teaching reading and their classroom practices. The study revealed that EFL teachers hold their belief system of teaching reading; however, their belief was incongruently implemented in the classroom. The above studies investigated issues quantitatively.

However, as to the best knowledge of the researchers, few local qualitative studies have been conducted to examine the relationship between EFL teachers' beliefs and application of reading comprehension strategies at secondary school level. For instance, Mekonnen (2020) conducted an exploratory case study of the pedagogic strategies that three secondary school EFL teachers apply in teaching reading comprehension during the different stages of reading. Likewise, through a descriptive interpretative case study design, Nurie (2017) examined the current practices of teachers in teaching reading and how the teachers handle and organize reading comprehension lessons. The above studies considered the general pedagogical issues in teaching reading and reading comprehension as well.

Hence, there seems to be a scarcity of qualitative case studies that examined the interplay between secondary school EFL teachers' beliefs and actual use of reading strategies in general and the post-reading strategies in particular in teaching reading comprehension lessons.

Therefore, EFL teachers have vital instructional role to put in practice and integrate the post-reading strategies in their actual reading comprehension lessons. This would in turn help students to be familiar with and do activities under such important reading comprehension strategies to extend their initial understanding of the text. In this study therefore, unlike the above local and studies from abroad, through a qualitative approach, an attempt was made to deeply examine the relationship between EFL teachers' beliefs and their actual use of post-reading strategies in teaching reading comprehension lessons. In view of that, the following research questions were formulated:

1. What beliefs do EFL teachers hold regarding the use of post-reading strategies in reading comprehension classes?
2. Which post-reading strategies do EFL teachers implement in their actual reading comprehension classes?
3. Do EFL teachers' beliefs match/mismatch their actual practices of post-reading strategies?

2. Methodology

2.1. Research Design

This exploratory case study is entirely qualitative. Qualitative research is an inquiry process of understanding a social or human problem, based on building a complex, holistic picture, formed with words, reporting detailed views of informants, and conducted in a natural setting. (Creswell, 2014). The qualitative approach helped the researchers carry out an in-depth investigation of the phenomena under study. Hence, to conduct this study, a case study design was chosen because the study was dealing with a single case, looking at a specific grade (Grade nine) and a specific number of participants (six EFL teachers) in a particular secondary school in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

2.2. Participants and Sampling

There are two secondary schools in the Sub-City of Lemi Kura, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. One is a private secondary school, and the other is government-owned. The target school chosen for the study was Edget Chora Secondary School, which is government-owned. Under the English department, 24 EFL teachers were teaching grades 9 up to 12 during data collection. The study was conducted in Addis Ababa, the researchers' current address, and in the neighboring secondary school where they dwell, primarily for practical reasons. It is obvious that the nature of the qualitative data to be generated needs rigorous procedures and extended time. Hence, it became a matter of feasibility to choose a research location where the researchers could easily contact the participants regularly.

Purposive sampling technique was employed to select the target school. Since the study followed a case study design, one government secondary

school was purposefully chosen. This school was preferred due to the fact that well experienced EFL teachers were available. The researchers were then convinced those EFL teachers can deliver substantial data regarding the issue of investigation compared to novice teachers available in the neighboring secondary school. The researchers were also familiar with the EFL teachers on duty in the target secondary school. This situation provided opportunity to ease data collection processes. Using the convenience sampling technique, therefore, among 10 ninth grade EFL teachers, six were selected and took part in the study based on their willingness. The researchers believed that it was not necessary to get additional EFL teachers involved in the study since voluntary participation has a key role to maintain ethical issues and to gather valuable qualitative data. Besides, the reason to choose only six cases (participants) was to ensure that the data generated by such limited participants would be manageable since the nature of a qualitative study is laborious. Regarding gender, the participants were all male EFL teachers since females were not willing to participate in the study.

The demographic information of the participants is presented in Table 1. To secure the anonymity and confidentiality of the information, short codes were given to each participant where, T1 = Teacher 1, T2 =Teacher 2, T3=Teacher3, T4=Teacher 4, T5=Teacher 5, and T6=Teacher 6.

Table 1

Demographic Information of Participants

No.	Participants	Gender	Age	Qualification	Teaching experience
1	T1	Male	40	B.Ed.	16 years
2	T2	Male	51	MA in TEFL	32 years
3	T3	Male	36	MA in TEFL	14 years
4	T4	Male	52	MA in TEFL	29 years
5	T5	Male	40	MA in TEFL	17 years
6	T6	Male	39	MA in TEFL	18 years

As regards the profile of participants shown in table 1, all of them were experienced teachers, with 14 up to 32 years of service. The age range of participants was 36-50. The data signified that they were matured enough. Hence, they could provide ample data regarding their beliefs and practices of the post-reading strategies in their respective reading comprehension classes. Except for one participant, five of them were MA degree holders in TEFL, so it was expected that they had taken relevant courses on teaching reading comprehension. Thus, the participants were likely to deliver valuable data concerning the issue under study.

2.3. Data Collection and Processing

2.3.1. Reading Comprehension Lesson Observation

Reading comprehension lesson observation was the major data collection tool in this study. By adopting a non-participant observation approach, twelve reading comprehension lesson observations were conducted. In promoting this approach, the researchers acted as an outsider

of the group of students and a teacher in the classroom being observed. During observation, in addition to audio recording, the researchers took field notes on accounts of particular events and how the participating EFL teachers practice the post-reading strategies in their reading comprehension classes.

2.3.2. Individual Interview

The purpose of the individual interview was to collect relevant data about the participating EFL teachers' beliefs and their actual practices of the post-reading strategies to assist students in becoming motivated and getting ready for reading and comprehending the given passage. The interview data were helpful in substantiating the observation data. The interview was conducted using a structured interview guide because every participant in a structured interview responds to the same question, so it was easier to find and compare responses during analysis. Furthermore, an associate professor of English language teaching at Addis Ababa University, Ethiopia double-checked the interview questions. In the end, the guide was adjusted in light of the suggestions. The final version of the interview guide comprised six questions. Three questions were devoted for the first and the second research questions of the study respectively. Here after are the sample interview questions used to collect data to respond to the first research question of the study.

1. What do you think is the instructional importance of post-reading strategies?
2. Do you believe that using post-reading strategies is time taking and unnecessary?
3. Which reading strategies do you believe should be frequently implemented?

The aforementioned interview questions were designed to address the first research question. These questions were designed based on the literature review and the researchers' insights. It was expected that EFL teachers' beliefs about application of post-reading strategies can be better understood by examining the nature of teachers' viewpoints regarding the advantage of post-reading strategies in teaching reading comprehension. It was also believed that teachers' beliefs can be revealed through considering their opinions about the instructional time allotment and the frequency of usage of post-reading strategies.

2.4. Data Collection Procedures

First, permission was obtained from the principal to collect data from the target secondary school. Second, the researchers maintained a good rapport with all grade nine EFL teachers to get approval of their participation

in lesson observations. Following this, using an information letter, the participants were made aware of the purpose of the study.

There were five units to be covered during the first semester of 2024 academic year, according to the Grade nine English annual lesson plans. Under each unit, there was one reading comprehension lesson. In sum, five reading comprehension lessons were expected to be covered within the semester.

To conduct the lesson observation smoothly, with the consent of the participants, two representative reading comprehension lessons were selected. (Unit 4: Reading Skills: National Park in Ethiopia, and Unit 5: Reading Skills: Horticulture). Hence, this situation was helpful in gathering observation data regarding EFL teachers' actual practices of post-reading strategies under similar frameworks of lessons and classroom contexts.

Observation data were collected focusing on the participants' endeavors in applying the post-reading strategies in reading comprehension classes. The lessons were not video recorded to avoid artificiality by teachers and to minimize frustration among the students. The researchers preferred to capture observation data by audio recording using unobtrusive recording tools i.e., cellphones. The audio data were transcribed immediately after each observation to avoid impulsive data loss. In addition, taking field notes was feasible since the reading comprehension instruction was going on at a manageable pace. Accordingly, the researchers took field notes to supplement the transcribed data. To aid the data analysis and interpretation work, based on the field notes (descriptive notes), the reflective notes were organized immediately after each observation. This situation was important to give meaning to the field notes taken during the lesson observations. Based on the observation schedule, the six participants were observed twice. In sum, twelve reading comprehension lesson observations were conducted. The lesson observations took 480 minutes. Two observation rounds per each participant were believed to be sufficient taking in to account the participants' willingness and time constraints. The lesson observation task was completed within four weeks.

The interview sessions were kept to the second phase of data collection to minimize artificial classroom behaviors that the participants may manifest during observation because of prior contamination of data, which might alert them about the study and might have affected the quality of data expected from the participants.

2.5. Ethical Issues

After a smooth relationship was maintained with the participants, the interview schedule was set with the respondents' full consent. Before the interview, the participants were given an information letter to make them aware of the purpose of the interview and ethical considerations. Then, they signed a consent form to confirm their willingness to participate in the study. Six EFL teachers who were teaching grade 9 students in the target secondary school and being observed also volunteered to participate in the interview sessions. The interview was carried out in Amharic (the Ethiopian native language) and translated later into English. This situation helped to avoid

the language barrier, which can possibly affect the quality and quantity of the expected data from the participants.

Next, after the researchers gained the participants' consent, all the individual interviews were audio-recorded using the Tecno DP10A tablet. We also took notes during the interview to avoid impulsive data loss. Therefore, the audio files were exported to NVivo-10 qualitative data analysis software to facilitate the data translation (Amharic into English) and verbatim transcription (changing audio data into textual data) work, which continued immediately after the interview sessions ended. To conduct a single individual interview, an average of 50 minutes was needed. The individual interviews started and finished within two weeks.

2.6. Data Analysis

The interview data were translated and transcribed consecutively. The interview transcripts were edited and repeatedly read for better understanding. The irrelevant and repeated interview items and the responses given were refined and polished from the transcripts. The NVivo-10 qualitative data analysis software was used to carry out the open coding process. In order not to miss important results that could be generated from the textual data, the open coding continued using the line-by-line coding technique. Primarily, the responses given for the first and second research questions regarding EFL teachers' beliefs and implementation of the post-reading strategies were coded, respectively. The results of the open coding of the data available under each sub issue were organized into parent and child nodes. The process was inductive and bottom-up (data-driven), moving from the particular to the general (from data to themes), and in the end, the data were interpreted (Creswell, 2014). As evidence, direct quotations taken from the individual interview transcripts were amalgamated in the narration of interview results.

For the observation data analysis, a reading comprehension lesson observation framework (RCLOF) adapted from Henk et.al. (2000) was used as a rubric. To ensure validity, the researchers aligned the content of the rubric with the study's research questions. This rubric was not directly used to collect observation data from the actual reading comprehension classes. However, it was applied to compare and contrast the observation data collected by means of audio recording and note-taking with the post-reading strategies incorporated in the rubric. This rubric was important to dig out and to double check the extent of the participants' application of the post-reading strategies while teaching reading comprehension using the three phase approach i.e., the pre, while and post reading phases.

3. Findings

This section of the study presents the results obtained from individual interviews and reading comprehension lesson observations (descriptive and reflective notes).

3.1. Results of the interview on EFL teachers' beliefs about the use of post-reading strategies in reading comprehension classes

The first research question was intended to explore beliefs the participating EFL teachers hold about the reading strategies that can be implemented in the post-reading phases of reading comprehension lessons. Six secondary school EFL teachers responded to the interview questions.

Table 2

The participants' beliefs about the instructional importance, necessity and frequency of usage of reading strategies

No.	Interview Question	Codes	Themes
1	What do you think is the instructional importance of post-reading strategies?	-Helps to check students' level of comprehension [T1].-The post -reading strategies help students to relate the information gained from the passage with their real life situation [T2].-The post-reading strategies help students to interpret the passage and connect it with their real life experiences [T3].-The post-reading strategies help them to do various related activities [T4].-The post-reading strategies help to check students' level of comprehension of the passage [T5].-Post-reading strategies help students to connect the theme of the passage with their real life experiences [T6].	-Interpreting the theme of the passage -Connecting the information gained from the passage with students' real-life experiences
2	Do you believe that using post-reading strategies is time taking and unnecessary?	-Beliefs that post-reading strategies are necessary; however, there is scarcity of time to handle such strategies [T1]. -If done according to plan, they are not time taking; most of the instructional time should be devoted to the while-reading strategies [T2].Believes that post-reading strategies are important [T3];Post-reading strategies are given less emphasis though they are important [T4].-Believes that except the negligence, post-reading strategies are necessary-Due to time constraints, I ignore the post-reading activities [T5].-The post-reading strategies are time-consuming [T6].	-Post-reading strategies are instructionally important -Post-reading strategies are time-consuming

3	Which reading strategies do you believe should be frequently implemented?	-Escape the pre-reading strategies due to shortage of instructional time; devote more time for the while- reading strategies [T1]. -Less emphasis is given to the post-reading strategies; beliefs most of the instructional time should be given for the while-reading strategies [T2]. -Devotes much of the instructional time for the while-reading strategies [T3]. -The aim of RC lesson is to help students develop the RC skills; beliefs much time should be given for the while-reading strategies [T4] -Post-reading strategies are inescapable; they are helpful to check students' overall comprehension [T5].-Beliefs that the aim of teaching reading is to assist students to comprehend the passage; Believes much time should be given for the while-reading strategies [T6].	-Neglecting the post-reading strategies -Devoting most of the instructional time to the while-reading strategies
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Theme No1: Beliefs about interpreting, and connecting the information available in the passage with students' real-life experiences

Interview Question 1 sought responses to the beliefs that participant EFL teachers hold about the instructional importance of implementing the post-reading strategies. The assumption behind this question is that if teachers believe that post-reading strategies are important, they are likely to implement these strategies during their reading comprehension instruction. According to the data, T2, T3, and T6 think that the post-reading strategies help students to interpret the theme of the passage and to connect it with the students' real-life experiences. T4 stated that the post-reading strategies help the students to do various related activities. Whereas, T1 and T5 said:

The post-reading strategies help to check students' level of comprehension of the passage. After reading the passage, students try to relate the information they gained from the passage with their day to day life experience and environment. After reading, students also try to evaluate the significance of the central themes of each paragraph, and compare and contrast ideas gained from the passage they are assigned to read.

Theme No.2: Beliefs about the instructional importance and time-consuming nature of post-reading strategies

Interview Question 2 aimed to explore whether the participants believe that using post-reading strategies during reading comprehension classes is time-consuming and unnecessary. T1, T2, T3, T4, and T5 believe that the post-reading strategies are necessary. However, they confess such strategies

require portions of the instructional time. Conversely, T1 said “The post-reading strategies are necessary; however, there is a scarcity of time to handle these strategies. T2 also whispered, “If done according to plan, the post-reading strategies are not time taking; however, most of the instructional time should be devoted to the while-reading strategies.” T3 described that post-reading strategies are instructionally important, but they are given less emphasis. In the same vein, T4 indicated that “except the negligence, the post-reading strategies are necessary, but, due to time constraints, I skip them.” Interestingly, T6 illustrated:

The post-reading strategies are time-consuming because the instructional time allowed to cover the reading comprehension lesson is inadequate. The reading comprehension lessons include many activities like reading and answering comprehension questions, skimming for general information, scanning for specific information, doing inference and reference questions, and finding antonyms and synonyms of key vocabulary. Therefore, without choice, English teachers must devote much of the instructional time to the while reading-strategies.

Theme No.3: Beliefs related to neglecting the post-reading strategies and giving much time to the while-reading strategies

Interview Question 3 was asked to get information about the reading strategies that the participants believe should be frequently implemented. T1, T2, T3, T4 and T6 noted that teaching reading aims to assist students in comprehending the passage, so they believe much attention should be given to the while-reading strategies. T1 said, “I skip the post-reading strategies due to a shortage of instructional time. Rather, I devote more time to the while-reading strategies.” T2 explained, “Less emphasis is given to the post-reading strategies; I believe most of the instructional time should be devoted to the while-reading strategies. Opposing other participants, T5 clarified, “The post-reading strategies are inescapable; they are helpful to check students' overall comprehension.” In sum, as the data exhibited the majority of the participants presume due to shortage of time, they neglect the post-reading strategies. They believe much of the instructional time should be devoted to the while-reading strategies.

3.2. Results of observation on implementation of the post-reading strategies

Three sample lesson observations are taken from the archives of field notes and transcriptions recorded during observations. These sample lessons are the representative lessons taken from three participant EFL teachers' reading comprehension classes. They are presented below to show evidences of reading comprehension lesson observations. [T1, T2, T3-stands for 'Teacher1' 'Teacher2' and 'Teacher3'; S-stands for 'Student']

Extract 1: A sample of Reading Lesson observation

Lesson 1: Reading: Unit Four: National Parks.

Post-reading phase [2:00-2:10 pm]

T1: Now, let us do the true or false questions on page 93. The natural beauty of Ethiopia amazes visitors with its mountains, savannah lands, lakes, and rivers.

S1: True (paragraph 1, line 2)

T1: Correct

T: Mount Tullu Dimtu is the highest peak in Ethiopia which stands at 4,377 meters.

S2: True (paragraph 4, line 6)

T1: Are you sure?

S3: No, it is false.

T1: Sure.

T1: Three endemic mammals are found in the Simien National Park.

S4: True (paragraph 8, line 5)

T1: Yeah, you are right.

T1: Alright, it is enough for today. Do matching questions on page 94 at home. Okay.

Extract 2: A sample of Reading Lesson observation

Lesson 2: Reading: Unit Five: Horticulture

Post-reading phase [9:59-10:10 am]

T2: All right. On page 111 there are comprehension questions, so let us do them together. Right? Answer the comprehension questions based on the passage. You have five minutes. Students get ready to do comprehension questions.

T2: "What are the most benefits of gardening?"

S2: To relieve stress

T2: What else?

S3: To get exercise

T2: Well. Gardeners can relieve stress and get exercise when they work in the garden.

T2: "According to the passage what does a gardener do?"

S4: A gardener cut flowers and vegetables.

T2: Yeah, a gardener cuts flowers and vegetables, what about others?

S5: A gardener enjoys a sense of accomplishment.

T2: Yeah, a gardener enjoys the sense of accomplishment. That is good. Now, let us do vocabulary questions related to the passage. Then, the teacher writes the following words on the whiteboard (relieve, unwind, contribute, consume, enhancing, instantaneous). Find the meanings of the following words based on the context given in the passage. You have five minutes to do.

Students copy the words in their exercise book and then begin to search for the contextual meanings of words in groups based on the passage.

T2: Now let us see the contextual meanings of words. What is the contextual meaning of the word 'relieve'?

S6: 'Reduce.'

T2: Yes, 'relieve' according to the passage means 'reduce'. What does 'Contribute' mean?

S7: 'impact'

T2: Correct. What does the word 'unwind' mean according to the passage?

S8: 'Unwind' means 'relax'.

T2: Yes, it is correct. Hence, on page 112, do exercises on 'prefixes' as homework. See you all next period.

S9: See you teacher.

Extract 3: A sample of Reading Lesson observation

Lesson 2: Reading Unit Five: Horticulture

Post-reading phase [1:59-2:10 p.m]

T3: Ok. Now let us focus on comprehension questions on page 111. Answer the following questions based on the passage you have already read. "Do you find it?"

Ss: "Yes, teacher"

T3: "What are the most benefits of gardening?"

S2: To relieve stress

T3: What about others?

S3: To get exercise

T3: Well. "According to the passage what does a gardener do?"

S4: A gardener cut flowers and vegetables.

T3: Correct, a gardener cuts flowers and vegetables, what else?

S5: A gardener enjoys a sense of accomplishment.

T3: Yeah, a gardener enjoys the sense of accomplishment.

T3: That is right. "What do vegetable gardeners know?"

S6: Where their product is coming from?

T3: Anyone else?

S7: Chemicals were used to grow produce.

T3: Ok that is fine. We run out of time, so on page 112, do exercises on prefixes at home. Goodbye students.

Ss: Goodbye teacher.

The observation data indicated that T1 let the students do post-reading questions available in the textbook. Though there is enough instructional time, he ignored the questions intended to extend students' understanding of the passage. He did not meaningfully implement the post-reading strategies. He gave the students matching questions as homework. He emphasized letting the students do comprehension questions rather than assisting them to extend their initial understanding of the passage, give more interpretations for the theme of the passage, and connect ideas with their real-life experiences. Likewise, T2, T3, T4, T5, and T6 help students do comprehension questions. They did not implement the post-reading strategies effectively. Depending on the ideas gained from the passage, they did not assist students in extending their understanding of the passage through discussions and oral reflections. By generating more questions after reading, the teachers did not try to assist students to interpret the theme of the passage and connect it with the real-life experiences of the students.

3.3. Results of the interview on implementation of post-reading strategies

The following section of the study report focuses on presenting the results of interview concerning the participants' report on implementation of the post-reading strategies. To obtain data, the interview participants were asked six questions. These questions were necessary to generate data regarding the post-reading strategies that the participants apply to extend the initial understanding of the passage, and to assist students in practicing the language skills in an integrated manner. Besides, the interview questions were important to obtain data related to the assistance given to students to help them interpret the core ideas of the given passage, and connect it with the real-life experiences of the students.

Table 3

Results of interview on implementation of post-reading strategies

No.	Interview Question	Codes	Themes
1	During the post-reading stage, what strategies do you use to help students extend their initial understanding of the text?	-After reading the passage, students do comprehension questions; They reflect on ideas they gained from the passage [T1].-Through general questions, and by letting students reflect on the theme of the passage, I check students' overall comprehension of the passage [T2].-Post-reading strategies are important to help students extend their understanding; Students do post-reading activities in the classroom and at home[T3] -Students become bored to extend their understanding of the passage during post-reading stage [T4].-Make students respond to comprehension questions turn by turn [T5]. -Students read the passage and comprehend accordingly [T6].	-Asking general questions, to let students reflect on the theme of the passage -Assisting the students in doing comprehension questions
2	During the post-reading stage, in what ways do you support your students to develop more meaningful interpretations about the meanings of the text and connect it to their-life situations?	-Ask the students more questions related to the passage to help them extend ideas gained form the passage [T1]. -After reading the passage, discuss on important issues to connect ideas with students' real-life experiences; Do not assign students to do more tasks after reading [T2].-Post-reading strategies are given very less attention [T3].-Due to students' demotivation and time constraints, post-reading strategies are usually ignored; Most of the instructional time is devoted to the while-reading strategies [T4].Encourage them to evaluate the significance of ideas taken from the passage [T5]-Students reflect orally about the theme of the passage[T6]	-Making the students discuss important issues -Asking them more questions related to the passage

3	How do you integrate speaking and writing activities related to the passage to help students extend their understanding?	-Make students write sentences and paragraphs to help them connect ideas of the passage with their real life experiences [T1]-Students reflect on some issues of the passage orally; they also write paragraphs when they respond to comprehension questions[T2]-Believes that skills integration is important to develop language skills; Students reflect orally on ideas gained from the passage; They write paragraphs related to the passage.[T3] -Students discuss orally and take notes while reading; Through skills integration, students digest the theme of the passage [T4] -Speak and write paragraphs while responding to comprehension questions; Students reflect on the theme of the passage orally[T5] -To learn skills in an integrated manner, students write the summary of the text [T6]	-Let the students discuss and reflect on ideas orally -Help them to take notes while reading, and write summary in the form of sentences and paragraphs
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Theme No.1. Asking general questions about the passage and letting the students do comprehension questions

Interview Question 1 aimed at digging out responses to the post-reading strategies that the participants use to help students extend their initial understanding of the passage after reading. This general question was intentionally asked to elicit the participant’s responses to the execution of the post-reading strategies. Accordingly, T1, T2, T5, and T6 replied that after reading the passage, they assist students in doing comprehension questions to extend their initial understanding of the passage. T2 said that through general questions, and by letting students reflect on the theme of the passage, he checks students' overall comprehension of the passage. T3 said that students do post-reading activities in the classroom and at home. Unlike others, T4 described that students usually become bored to extend their understanding of the passage during the post-reading phase.

Theme No.2. Making the students interpret and connect ideas taken from the passage with their real-life experiences

Interview Question 2 focuses on the participants’ endeavors to implement the post-reading strategies to support their students to develop more interpretations of ideas of the passage and connect it to their real-life experiences. Hence, T1 asks students more questions related to the passage to help them extend ideas gained from the passage. T2 makes students discuss important issues to connect ideas taken from the passage with their real-life experiences. T6 encourages students to reflect orally on the theme of the passage to make them extend their initial understanding of the text and connect it with their real-life experiences. T3 and T4 explained that they usually give less emphasis or ignore the post-reading strategies. T5 said, “I encourage students to evaluate the significance of ideas taken from the

passage.” T6 reported that students reflect orally about the theme of the passage.

Theme No.3.Maintaining language skills integration

Interview Question 3 focused on revealing whether the participants integrated speaking and writing activities related to the passage during the post-reading stage to help students extend their initial understanding. T1, T2, T3, T4, T5 and T6 reported that after reading, they assist students in discussing ideas of the passage and reflect them orally. Likewise, they said that they help students write summary sentences and paragraphs related to the passage.

The results from the reading comprehension lesson observations revealed that during the post-reading stage, all of the participants instructed the students to do comprehension questions based on the given passage. Some students who have access to the textbook try to skim the passage and search for evidence. Nevertheless, the majority of the students sit idle since they don't have access to textbooks. Within the small groups, very few students who can read the textbook respond to the comprehension questions randomly. Most of the participants ignore the post-reading questions available in the textbook and focus on other comprehension questions. They assign students to do comprehension questions at home. The participants did not assist the students in discussing and reflecting on ideas gained from the passage to extend their initial understanding. By generating more questions after reading, the participants did not assist students to interpret the theme of the passage and connect it with the real-life experiences of the students.

In sum, in implementing the post-reading strategies, therefore, the interview and observation results are consistent in some way that both interview and observation data revealed that the participants emphasize assigning students to do comprehension questions both in the classroom and at home. At the post-reading stage, as the interview and observation results exhibited, the majority of the participants did not assist students in evaluating the passage, extending their initial understanding, giving more interpretations to the main ideas of the passage, and connecting such ideas with the real-life experiences of the students.

3.4. The Relationship between EFL Teachers' Beliefs and actual Practices of Post-reading Strategies

The third research question was intended to investigate the correspondence between EFL teachers' beliefs and their actual practices of the post-reading strategies. The interview data were helpful to examine the belief systems that the target secondary school EFL teachers hold about the use of post-reading strategies. On the other hand, using observation it was possible to scrutinize the participants' actual practices of post-reading strategies in reading comprehension classes. Therefore, the results of data obtained through interview and observation in relation to the third research questions has been presented in the above section. (See the results for the first and the second research question above). Here the summary of results

of data obtained using the interview and observation in line with the first and the second research question were compared and contrasted to identify whether the results were compatible or not.

The interview results indicated the participants ask general questions, let students reflect on the theme of the passage orally and assist the students in doing comprehension questions to help them extend the initial understanding of the text. To connect the theme of the passage with students' real life experiences, the participants stated that they make the students discuss important issues and ask the students more questions related to the passage. Finally, to assist students in practicing language skills through integration, they help the students discuss and reflect on ideas orally. Besides, they support the students to take notes while reading, and write summary in the form of sentences and paragraphs after reading the given passage.

However, the observation data exhibited the participants did not implement the post-reading strategies satisfactorily. Rather, they ignore the post-reading activities that initiate the students to apply appropriate post-reading strategies. The teachers give the students post-reading activities to do at home or they completely reject those activities. Additionally, as the observation results exhibited, the majority of the participants did not assist the students in evaluating the passage, extending initial understanding, giving more interpretations to the main ideas of the passage, and connecting such ideas with experiences of the students.

4. Discussion

This qualitative study intends to explore some secondary school EFL teachers' beliefs and application of the post-reading strategies in teaching reading comprehension. To attain the research objectives, data were collected using interviews and lesson observations. Henceforth, the results of the study are presented sequentially in line with the first, the second and the third research questions of the study and discussed in light of the related studies.

The results of interview data revealed that most of the participating EFL teachers believe the post-reading strategies are important. They presume the post-reading strategies help students to interpret the theme of the passage and connect it with their real-life experiences. Furthermore, they are of the view that the post-reading strategies are necessary. However, they believe such strategies require sufficient time. The participants also reported that to implement the post-reading strategies, there is scarcity of time. Therefore, they consider more time should be devoted to the implementation of the while-reading strategies. These results are similar to several studies (e.g. Varol, 2010; Çakici, 2017; Atinafu, 2018) which stated that EFL teachers generally believe the necessity of reading strategies almost in all stages. Nevertheless, the post-reading strategies are the least preferred strategies. Therefore, such results imply that teachers give value to the post-reading strategies and perceive them as instructionally important. However, compared to the pre- and while-reading strategies, they did not prefer to apply them in the actual reading comprehension classes due to several reasons. Consequently, the students will not be able to get familiar with the

post-reading strategies. The students also did not get opportunity to interpret the text they have already gone through and extend their initial understanding of the text beyond the classroom.

To supplement the data analysis, the researchers compare and contrast the observation data (the transcribed data and field notes) concerning implementation of post-reading strategies with the reading comprehension lesson observation framework (RCLOF) or the rubric adapted from (Henk et al., 2000). Thus, the data show that the participating teachers did not encourage the students to extend their initial understanding of the passage by reflecting on their personal opinions. Using different strategies, the teachers did not assist the students in relating the text with their real-life experiences. Similarly, teachers did not let the students summarize the passage after reading orally or through writing. These findings did not go in line with studies (e.g., Khoshsima, 2014; Qomariyah, 2020; Imran Ahmed, et al., 2024) which revealed that summarization techniques seem to be plausible to improve the students' reading comprehension. This result implies during the post-reading stage, the students lack opportunity to practice language in an integrated manner through writing as a follow up to reading activity. Furthermore, the participants did not apply strategies to assist the students in doing activities such as wiring sentences and paragraphs as a follow-up to reading. Also, the participants did not apply strategies to encourage the students to do any speaking activities such as group discussions, retelling what they have read, debates or arguments, expression of opinions, and oral summary as a follow-up to reading activity. Besides, the teachers did not apply strategies that help the students to appreciate, react to, and state feelings of interest or any other emotional responses to the author's ideas or feelings after reading the passage.

Observation data revealed a limited implementation of post-reading strategies. Teachers often delegated post-reading activities as homework or omitted them entirely, indicating a lack of emphasis on extending students' comprehension beyond the classroom. This pattern may suggest a potential disconnect between teachers' recognition of the value of these strategies and the practical constraints they face, such as limited instructional time or insufficient training on how to integrate post-reading strategies effectively. This findings go in line with some studies (e.g., Ozek & Civelek, 2006; Çakici, 2017; Varol, 2010) which specified that the teachers employ the pre-, and while-reading strategies. Nevertheless, the post-reading strategies did not get much attention. This situation may happened due to several reasons such as shortage of instructional time, lack of appropriate lesson plan, lack of teachers' commitment to apply post reading strategies, insufficient teacher training, and lack of motivation and interest of the students to extend their understanding of the passage after reading.

Nevertheless, the interview results revealed that the participants apply the post-reading strategies such as asking general questions, letting students reflect on the theme of the passage, and assisting the students in doing comprehension questions to extend the students' initial understanding

of the text. To assist the students in developing more meaningful interpretations about the meanings of the text and to connect it to their real-life experiences, the participants make the students discuss important issues and ask them more questions related to the passage. In order to integrate speaking and writing activities related to the passage to help students extend their initial understanding of the passage, the participants apply the post-reading strategies such as letting the students discuss and reflect on ideas orally, take notes while reading, and write summary in the form of sentences and paragraphs.

Meanwhile, both the interview and observation data revealed a discrepancy between teachers' positive views on the instructional importance of post-reading strategies and their actual classroom practices. Although the teachers acknowledged the value of these strategies, they perceived them as time-consuming and instructionally demanding. These findings go in line with some studies done at secondary schools level. For instance, the study done by Al-husban (2019) revealed that most of the observed and interviewed teachers knew the names of the reading comprehension strategies and the stages of teaching reading comprehension. However, they did not know how to employ and practice them. Khonamri & Salimi, (2010) and Kuzborska (2011) on the other hand investigated the interplay between EFL high school teachers' beliefs and their instructional practices of reading strategies. The results have shown that there was some discrepancy between teachers' beliefs and their self-reported practices. Çak (2016) found out that secondary school EFL teachers believe in the necessity of the reading strategies, and they prefer to use them almost at all stages. Besides, the results of the study show that post-reading strategies are the least preferred. These findings imply that though teachers possess positive beliefs about the instructional importance of post-reading strategies, their beliefs could not be translated in to practice. This might be due to teachers' lack of awareness of these strategies due to insufficient training. Also, it might be attributed to teachers' inability to implement the post-reading strategies due to inadequacy of instructional time and lack of motivation of students to extend discussions, interpret, evaluate and summarize the text after reading. In turn, the students lose opportunity to extend their initial understanding of the passage and connect its theme with their real-life experiences. In addition, such results may be attributed to methodological limitations such as small sample size and short observation duration which can affect the results of this study.

5. Conclusions

Based on the findings, it seems reasonable to conclude that regardless of the positive views of the participants about the instructional advantage of post-reading strategies, they presume these strategies are time-consuming

and instructionally demanding. Hence, most of them incline towards the necessity of implementing the while-reading strategies by giving less attention to the post-reading strategies. This situation may actually hamper the required support that should be given by the teachers to the students during the post-reading phase. Thus, the teacher and the students may not sufficiently achieve the intended reading comprehension lesson objectives. In turn, the students' reading comprehension skills may not improve as required.

On the other hand, the interview data indicated that the participants reported that they use few post-reading strategies. Conversely, the observation results indicated that the majority of the participating EFL teachers did not implement the post-reading strategies efficiently. Therefore, these findings may suggest that the participants do not show a persistent instructional role in implementing the post-reading strategies. Students may not become familiar with the post-reading strategies. Consequently, they may not achieve the intended instructional objectives of either comprehending the given passage or becoming independent and strategic readers in the long run. Particularly, this situation may affect the reading habit of students as well as their overall academic achievement since reading is a crucial receptive skill.

Furthermore, as the findings from interview data revealed, the participating EFL teachers acknowledged the value of post-reading strategies. However, all of the participants did not implement these strategies satisfactorily in the actual reading comprehension classes. This vividly indicates the discrepancy between teachers' positive views on the instructional importance of post-reading strategies and their actual practices of such strategies during the post-reading phase. This situation indicates that participants are not likely to assist students both to become familiar with and apply the post-reading strategies efficiently. This results in inability of the students to apply post-reading strategies either in reading comprehension classes or in other nonacademic reading contexts.

6. Future Research in the area

Future research could build on these findings by examining students' awareness and beliefs about post-reading strategies to gain a more holistic understanding of the challenges in teaching reading comprehension. Additionally, this study's limitations, such as the small sample size, only male participants, and brief observation periods, highlight the need for larger, more diverse samples and extended observation durations and inclusion of female teachers. Researchers might also investigate contextual factors, such as curriculum constraints, teacher training, and student motivation, that influence the implementation of post-reading strategies. Adopting mixed-methods or longitudinal approaches could provide richer insights into how both male and female EFL teachers can effectively integrate post-reading strategies into their instructional practices.

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